

RePluris: Identification of patients with multiple chronic conditions at risk of readmission. Role of patient-reported outcome measures. Study protocol

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Summary

Social determinants are associated with the likelihood of readmission and death in patients with multiple conditions. At the same time, the population with multiple chronic conditions is ageing, making individuals more vulnerable to readmission when their preference is often to stay at home.

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Objective:

To create and validate predictive models of hospital readmission and mortality in the transition period after discharge (1 month) and at 1 year in patients with multiple chronic conditions, including variables related to patients and their environment.

Design: This is a quasi-quantitative study: first phase: a qualitative study based on a focus group of patients/caregivers and a nominal group (or expert panel), composed of professionals (doctors, nurses, and social workers), in both cases, with the objective of identifying and exploring factors that the participants believe to be most important in the occurrence of readmissions; and a second phase: a prospective observational cohort involving five hospitals in three autonomous regions (Andalusia, Catalonia, and the Basque Country) in Spain. Patients are required to meet two or more of the criteria developed by Ollero. Based on the data gathered in these focus groups of patients/caregivers and nominal groups of professionals, we will identify variables for inclusion in the final models together with clinical variables, and patient and caregiver self-reported outcome measures (health-related quality of life, caregiver burden, and social support). Logistic/Cox regression models to predict the risk of readmission and death **will be** developed and validated internally and validated in an external cohort.

Expected results: We hope to provide the health system with stratification tools for patients with multimorbidity to help identify those most needing personalized interventions.

Keywords: *multimorbid patients, readmissions.*

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1. Background

Improvements in living conditions, as well as in social and healthcare systems, have led to increases in life expectancy in most of the world. In Europe, the percentage of the population over 65 years of age will rise from 18.9% in 2015 to around 29% in 2080. We live longer and survive many diseases, but the price we are paying is a growth in chronic conditions, in the last years of our lives.(1)

This new social and epidemiological trend is becoming a key factor to consider in developing medium- and long-term strategies in most healthcare systems. Nowadays, appropriate management of multimorbidity is considered critical to the sustainability of these systems.(2) Patients with multiple chronic conditions (MCCs) are the clinical paradigm of the emergence of multimorbidity in our societies. They meet all the criteria for the so-called ‘populations with complex chronic diseases’: they are prevalent in most clinical arenas, and correspond to individuals who are of advanced age (the mean age of patients with MCCs in multicenter cohorts being around 75–80 years), complex, clinically vulnerable, and prone to functional decline, and have high readmission and mortality rates.

One approach to reducing readmission rates has been to implement risk prediction models to identify and target interventions towards those at most risk of early readmission. Unfortunately, most readmission risk prediction models have been found to perform poorly and not yet be useful in clinical settings.(3) More recently, these findings were corroborated by a systematic review by Zang et al, which noted that while risk prediction models are growing in number and condition specificity, they show only moderate discriminative ability.(4) Such models have typically focused on the risk characteristics of the patients and not characteristics of institutional behavior that might put patients at risk. In addition to institutional variables that influence readmission, our research team hypothesizes that there are social and patient/caregiver-related factors that lead to repeat admissions and even deaths that the healthcare system is currently failing to identify and address.

We designed this project under the auspices of the Spanish Research Network on Chronicity, Primary Care and Health Promotion (RICAPPS). This network focuses on three major issues: the challenge of managing the phenomenon of chronicity, a desire for more and better information in this field, and a need to increase research capacity in the fields of health policies and services in Spain.

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The overall goal of the RePluris research project is to identify which patients with multimorbidity are most likely to be readmitted or die and assess the role of patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) in identifying this population. Our objective in this paper is to outline the design of the RePluris-Pro prospective study. To our knowledge, this is the first study with this comprehensive perspective in Spain, considering not only clinical and economic outcomes but also PROMs.

The specific study objectives are: 1.-to identify new factors related to patients (quality of life, functional dependence, social support, substance abuse) and also caregivers (caregiver burden, social support) that are associated with the likelihood of readmission and mortality in the transition period after discharge (defined as up to 1 month after the index episode) and up to 1 year after the index episode; 2.-to create and internally validate rules for predicting readmission and mortality in the transition period after discharge and up to 1 year after the index episode based on data from the index episode, and assess their external validity in an independent cohort of patients; and 3. - to identify differences between patients who are and are not readmitted in the discharge transition period. To address these objectives, we will initially conduct a preliminary qualitative study to identify the needs and expectations of patients and professionals and then express them in the form of variables that can be incorporated into statistical models.

2. Methods

Design and setting: RePluris is a mixed design study:

Phase 1 - Qualitative study using a focus group of patients/caregivers and a nominal group (or expert panel) of professionals (doctors, nurses, and social workers). In both cases, the objective is to explore and identify the factors that the participants considered to be the most important in the occurrence of readmissions, and then, transform the concepts identified into measurable variables that could be included in the predictive models to be developed in the quantitative phase.

2nd phase- Prospective cohort design. We will recruit patients in five hospitals in three Spanish regions (Andalusia, Catalonia, and the Basque Country). All the hospitals belong to the Spanish National Public Health System and offer universal care that is almost free at the point of delivery to residents. Table 1 lists each participating hospital and the corresponding region.

Study Population: We will include individuals over 18 years of age before discharge from the Geriatric or Internal Medicine Departments following admission for acute episodes related to or

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decompensation/exacerbation of a previously diagnosed chronic condition, or *de novo* conditions, who are classified as patients with MCCs as they met the Ollero criteria.(5)

The exclusion criteria are admission for end-of-life care, scheduled procedures, exacerbation of a rheumatic or systemic disease, work-up of anemia in patients with unknown comorbidities, and tests for neoplasia and acute processes without associated comorbidities. In addition, patients will be excluded if they did not sign an informed consent form, were untraceable due to a change of address, or withdrew from the study during the follow-up period.

We have also collected socio-demographic and clinical data on patients lost to follow-up. Figure 1 shows the expected flow of patients through the study.

Information and data collection:

1st phase: For the focus group of patients and caregivers, a list of patients readmitted in the last 3 months will be retrieved, and a random number sequence generated and used to select who is to be called to be invited to the meeting. For the nominal group of professionals, the research team of this project will identify doctors, nurses, and social workers who have relevant experience and are likely to participate. Before inclusion, it is confirmed that patients, carers, and professionals are able to participate and have given their consent; in addition, any whose state of health might prevent their full participation will be excluded. Two people with experience in qualitative methodology will facilitate the sessions, one moderating and formulating the questions, and the other taking notes on the main themes that emerge. (doi:10.5281/zenodo.13903348)

2nd phase:

During hospital admission, study staff will inform patients and their caregivers about the study. They will provide an informed consent form to those who agree to participate and help them to complete the PROM and caregiver-reported outcome measure questionnaires when appropriate: once recruited and once patients have reached clinical stability and are due to be discharged (Figure 2). To succeed in gathering data before patient discharge, trained interviewers will assist participants and check that all the information is properly documented. To increase the response rate, non-responders at discharge will be called on days 2 and 7 offering them the option to respond over the phone. Clinical background, use of healthcare resources, data related to readmission, and death at 1 year will be automatically extracted from electronic medical records. These data will be collected and managed using Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) tools hosted at Osakidetza. (6,7)

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REDCap is a secure, web-based software platform designed to support data capture for research studies, providing 1) an intuitive interface for validated data capture; 2) audit trails for tracking data manipulation and export procedures; 3) automated export procedures for seamless data downloads to common statistical packages; and 4) procedures for data integration and interoperability with external sources. Management staff at each hospital will provide information on hospital characteristics

Variables:

1. Exposure variables

a. Social variables

- i. *Sociodemographic variables*. Date of birth; level of education; marital status; place of origin and destination when discharged (home; home of a relative; temporary or permanent nursing home; long-term stay social-healthcare center; another acute healthcare center); whether the patient routinely lives in the same place and with the same people (yes/no); whether the patient usually takes care of someone else (yes/no/partially); and perception of weight loss in the last 6 months (yes/no).
- ii. *Related to the help needed and received before and after admission*. Help received for managing financial affairs; using the phone and preparing or administering medication (yes/no); care provider before and after admission (first-degree relative [spouse; children; siblings; family unit]; second-degree relative [others]; friends; neighbors; social volunteers; formal caregivers [whether visiting or live-in]; nursing home services; support needed but not received; not identified; not applicable due to being self-sufficient); receipt of social assistance (yes/no) and if so; origin (public/private); quantity (time per week or amount [€] per month) and request status (during admission/already processed/already operative) and type (external help for daily chores and self-care; dependency benefit or other type of financial support; home-based telecare; admission to a day-center nursing home or temporary social-healthcare center).
- iii. *Use of health resources*.
 1. In the last year (yes/no): Emergency services; hospital admission and primary care attendances (if so; number of times); and follow-up in a chronic disease program.

2. Related to admissions: Dates of emergency department attendance; hospital admission and discharge; department of admission (internal medicine/other).
 3. Related to follow-up: Inclusion in a chronic disease program or individualized plan (yes/no); department (primary care; short or medium-stay units/centers; care under the hospital-at-home program; palliative care unit; geriatric day hospital; and pathology-specific care programs such as the heart failure program or similar; or hospital outpatient clinics).
- b. Clinical variables.
- i. *Classification by Ollero's criteria* before and after admission.(5)
 - ii. *Pre-admission comorbidities* (yes/no): high blood pressure; diabetes mellitus; dyslipidemia; chronic renal failure and if so; glomerular filtration rate as estimated by the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration at baseline (i.e., pre-admission status); chronic heart failure and if so; left ventricle ejection fraction and the New York Heart Association value; ischemic heart disease; atrial fibrillation; stroke; asthma; chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD); cognitive impairment; dementia; history of cancer and if so; ongoing or previous treatment and curative or palliative intent; smoking habit and if so; former (>1 year) or current; history of alcohol abuse and if so; former (>1 year) or current; musculoskeletal system disorder; history of hip fracture; visual impairment; history of eye surgery (cataract surgery, other); depression; anxiety; prostatic disease; hearing impairment; venous insufficiency; any fall in the last 6 months and if so; injury and fracture (yes/no); and peripheral arterial disease.
 - iii. *Functional situation recorded by the clinician* (yes/no): at baseline (self-sufficient/requiring assistance with Barthel-assessed basic or instrumental activities; usually/hardly/never going outside; walking with or without assistance/barely able to walk/bedridden/using wheelchair) and after discharge (able to walk/able to sit on a couch/bedridden; requiring feeding tube or urinary catheter).(8,9)
 - iv. *Long-term home therapy before and after admission*: proton pump inhibitor or similar (omeprazole; pantoprazole; other); diabetes medication (insulin; metformin; sodium-glucose cotransporter inhibitors; dipeptidyl peptidase-4

inhibitors; sulfonylureas; glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists; meglitinides; glitazones; others); antihypertensive agent (angiotensin-converting-enzyme inhibitors; angiotensin receptor blockers; beta-blockers; amlodipine or similar; diltiazem or verapamil; doxazosin); other cardiovascular treatment (i) (amiodarone; digoxin; isosorbide; ivabradine; sacubitril-valsartan); diuretic (hydrochlorothiazide; chlorthalidone; potassium-sparing diuretics; acetazolamide; indapamide; indapamide; amiloride; furosemide elastomeric pump); hypolipidemic drug (statins; fibrates; ezetimibe; proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type-9); antiplatelet therapy (acetylsalicylic acid; clopidogrel; other); anticoagulant (vitamin K antagonist; apixaban; dabigatran; edoxaban; rivaroxaban); other cardiovascular treatment (ii) (folic acid; cyanocobalamin; oral iron; erythropoietin); musculoskeletal injuries (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; paracetamol; metamizole; tramadol; allopurinol; bisphosphonates; calcium or vitamin D); neurological agent (opioids; antidepressants; haloperidol; risperidone; quetiapine; antimentia; antiparkinsonians; antipsychotics; anticonvulsants; anxiolytics); for infections (antibiotics; antivirals; antifungals); endocrine medications (corticosteroids; levothyroxine; thyroid medications; others); urological medications (alfuzosin; tamsulosin; dutasteride); respiratory system medications (beta-2 adrenergic agonists; inhaled corticosteroids; anticholinergics; leukotriene modifiers; theophylline; oxygen therapy; non-invasive mechanical ventilation); anti-cancer therapy (ongoing conventional chemotherapy; immunotherapy); immunosuppressant (methotrexate; biologics; others); and the total number of medications prescribed.

- v. *Vaccination* (yes/no): flu vaccine in the last year; pneumococcal vaccine in last 5 years; SARS-CoV-2 vaccine and if so; number of doses and whether a vector-based vaccine had been given (yes/no).
- vi. *Presumptive and definitive diagnosis* (yes/no): heart failure; stroke; bronchitis; pneumonia; COPD exacerbation; urinary tract infection (UTI); ischemic heart disease; arrhythmia (any type); sepsis (any location); coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19); constitutional syndrome; metabolic impairment; anemia; cancer with any complications; confusional syndrome; impaired renal function; other diagnosis; number of diagnoses.

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- vii. *Complications during admission* (yes/no): acute renal failure; acute respiratory failure; intestinal obstruction; hemorrhage requiring transfusion; venous thrombosis; urinary retention; cardiovascular events (hypotension; cardiorespiratory arrest; acute myocardial infarction; pulmonary edema; ventricular tachycardia); treatment-related events (diarrhea secondary to antibiotics; digoxin toxicity; hypoglycemia; ketoacidosis or hyperosmolar coma); infections (bacteremia; cellulitis; nosocomial pneumonia; nosocomial UTI; COVID-19; asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 infection); neurological events (delirium; stroke; cognitive impairment); generic events (malnutrition; depression; constipation; accidental fall; pressure ulcer; process-related complications; other complications); hyponatremia; anemia; pulmonary embolism (PE); others; need for intensive care unit admission.
- viii. *Score on a Frailty index for rapid geriatric assessment (the Frail-VIG index)* on discharge (10)
- ix. *Charlson comorbidity index* on discharge (11)
- x. *Score on an index predicting risk of death in patients with MCCs (the PROFUND index)* on discharge (12)
- c. PROMs
 - i. *5-level EuroQoL health-related quality of life questionnaire (EQ-5D-5L)* (13)
 - ii. *Adherence to Refill and Medications Scale (ARMS)* (14)
 - iii. *Barthel Index* (9)
 - iv. *Modified Gijon Social and Family Evaluation Scale* (15)
- d. Caregiver-reported outcome measures
 - i. *EQ-5D-5L* (13)
 - ii. *12-item Zarit Burden Interview (ZBI)* (16)
 - iii. *Age*
- e. Number of consultations over the phone and face-to-face with doctors and/or nurses and the corresponding department during the first month after discharge, and 1-year follow-up of the number of attendances to emergency services; number of hospital admissions and death.

2. Outcomes

- a. Readmissions in the transitional period of 30 days after discharge
- b. Readmissions up to 1 year after discharge

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c. 1-month to 1-year mortality

Figure 2 summarizes the data collection process in participating hospitals.

Safety and ethical considerations

As appropriate, permission to use the questionnaires has been obtained from all developers of the instruments used, including the EuroQoL Research Foundation. Trained research staff will inform eligible patients about the study verbally and in writing; and written informed consent will be obtained from all participants before enrollment. Patients may withdraw from the study at any time; during recruitment or follow-up; and all data collected will be treated as confidential. All participating hospitals have staff available to answer any questions that the patient or family members may have about the research.

The study was approved by the Basque Research Ethics Committee (Reference number PI2018191), and registered with Clinical Trials.gov (Reference number: NCT05574790).

Follow-up

In all participating hospitals, data will be retrieved on all the medical and nursing visits within 1 month after discharge. Further, emergency department attendance and readmission up to 1 year after discharge will be recorded.

Sample size

For predictive model development, it has been stated that at least 10 events of the main dependent variable of interest (in our case, readmissions) are needed for each independent variable included in a multivariate logistic regression model. Since we intend to include a limited but comprehensive set of variables in the multivariate model (expected to be no less than 10), we have estimated that at least 100 events of the dependent variable in the derivation sample will be necessary to ensure that the regression model converged adequately. Data from our hospitals suggests that the events of the dependent variable readmission per month will correspond to at least 12% of cases. Table 2 summarizes the n in each hospital.

Missing data assumptions and recoding of variables

Data are to be considered “missing” if we lack information on any of the following variables: comorbidities before admission, medications and home therapy, presumptive diagnoses on admission,

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complications during admission, items from the Frail-VIG index, certain diagnoses at discharge, treatments and medications at discharge, and emergency department and inpatient readmissions. The depression and anxiety variables will be grouped into a single variable called 'mood disorders', and similarly, cognitive impairment and dementia into a variable called 'altered mental status'. Groups will be created according to the nature of the complications recorded, two large groups: medical complications and geriatric complications. Further, within medical complications, we envisage classifying complications as: neurological, hematological, digestive, cardiovascular, urinary tract, infectious, electrolyte-related, respiratory, endocrine, or drug-related complications, and within the group of geriatric complications, as delirium, malnutrition, pressure ulcers, or falls.

Statistical analysis

1. - Descriptive statistics: Mean and standard deviations will be calculated for continuous variables if normally distributed (and otherwise, medians and interquartile ranges) and frequencies and percentages for qualitative variables.
2. -Bivariate analysis: The Student's t-test or the non-parametric Wilcoxon test (for non-normal distributions) will be applied for two-level outcomes; and analysis of variance or a Kruskal-Wallis test (for non-normal distributions) where the outcome variable has three or more categories. Otherwise, for categorical variables, the Chi-square test (or Fisher's Exact method, as appropriate) will be used. Multivariate models will be developed where appropriate to adjust for confounders.
3. -Creation and validation of predictive models: Predictive models will be created using Cox/logistic proportional hazards models. These models will be validated using the validation cohort. The sensitivity, specificity, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) will be calculated and compared with the results obtained using the derivation cohort. The calibration of the models will be evaluated using the Hosmer-Lemeshow test, and their discrimination capacity using receiver operating characteristic curves. Additionally, multilevel analysis will be performed to adjust for the effect of hospital of admission in the previous multivariate results. The performance of the models generated in the validation cohort will be assessed in terms of discriminative capacity (AUC) and calibration (comparing the predicted probabilities of the original model and those observed in the validation cohort).

Quality assurance

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The reviewers have been provided with a handbook, designed by the principal investigator together with clinical collaborators, and received specific instructions for the identification and collection of relevant data. During the study, the principal investigator and clinical collaborators will supervise the process. Each reviewer from each participating hospital has a specific username and password to access REDCap. Personal data identifying individuals will be separated from the clinical data and patient and caregiver self-reported outcomes. Patient identification numbers will always be used for data management. In addition, each hospital has a project manager to help reviewers, coordinate the study, and ensure that all processes follow good practice. Once a month, the quality of the data collection process is assessed.

Duration of the project

The project is expected to last 2 years divided into recruitment (1 year) and follow-up (1 year). At least 6 months are expected to be required to complete error detection and data repair (database cleaning).

Project management

The coordination committee responsible for all decisions is comprised of all study leaders. This study has four leaders from three research groups belonging to RICAPPS who are responsible for each of the objectives. Dr. Susana García-Gutiérrez is responsible for the general coordination as well as the evaluation and development of predictive models of readmission and mortality. Dr. Raul Quirós is responsible for evaluation and development of predictive models for deterioration and complications during hospitalization. Dr Anna Renom is responsible for the validation of the Frail-VIG index and the influence of its score on outcomes, and Dr. J Ternero for the characterization of complex patients who do not have MCCs.

3. Discussion

Across the participating hospitals, we hope to recruit more than 500 patients. Table 3 summarizes the basic characteristics of the participating patients and Table 4 the characteristics of the caregivers. Analyses of both patient and caregiver data will be stratified by patient readmission within 30 days after discharge.

Problems envisaged

The main problems we expect to encounter in this study are related to the rate of response rate and difficulty in obtaining all the data required. To reduce the risks of low response rates and high losses to follow-up, great efforts will be made by a trained research assistant and the physicians and other collaborators participating in the study to explain the objectives of the study to patients. A research assistant trained specifically for the study will administer questionnaires on the day of discharge. Patients will be given the option of completing the questionnaires over the phone upon request, up to 7 days after discharge. To minimize the difficulties related to data retrieval from health records, all reviewers have received specific training, as well as a handbook to help them with the follow-up process.

Expected outcomes of the study

The results of this coordinated project will generate scientifically valid and clinically and socially important information to inform the decision-making of managers, the people who are responsible for ensuring equality in the care process as well as in health outcomes. For clinicians, we will develop clinical prediction rules, which would serve as the basis for software applications for clinical decision support. Specifically, our intention is to create tools that will be easy to use, and preferably straightforwardly integrated into electronic health records. This would allow physicians and patients themselves to consider the individual risk at the time of appointments, to guide their decision-making.

Dissemination of results and publication policy

RePluris-working group has established that, for publication purposes, an author has to have contributed to each of the following activities: 1) conception/design and/or analysis/interpretation, 2) writing of the manuscript, and 3) approval of the final version, and take public responsibility for the content of the paper. All co-authors have to review and agree with the contents of the manuscript as submitted. Study and manuscripts will follow the STROBE guidelines for conducting and disseminating observational studies and the TRIPOD-AI statement for reporting of a multivariable prediction model for individual prognosis or diagnosis. The main study results will be disseminated in the media. The main results of the project will also be linked to Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13884984>)

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FIGURE 1: Expected flow chart of patients through the study

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Figure 2. *Data collection process.*

ARMS; Adherence and Refill of Medications Scale; PROM; Patient-reported outcome measure; ZBI; Zarit Burden Interview

Tables

Table 1. Participating hospitals by region

Region	Hospital	Valid patients
Andalusia; Málaga	Hospital Costa del Sol	103
Andalusia; Sevilla	Hospital Virgen del Rocío	82
Basque Country; Bizkaia	Hospital Galdakao-Usansolo	247
Catalonia; Barcelona	Centre Fòrum from Hospital del Mar	103
Catalonia; Barcelona	Centre L'Esperança from Hospital del Mar	
Total		535

Table 2: Basic description of the participating patients by readmission status

	Total N=535	Missing N(%)	Readmitted within 30 days after discharge		p-value
			No (n=445)	Yes (n=90)	
Age, years	82.3(10)	1(0.2)	82(10)	83.8(9.3)	0.1313
Sex					0.3469
male	279 (52.1)		228 (51.2)	51 (56.7)	
female	256 (47.9)		217 (48.8)	39 (43.3)	
Number of defined categories					
Category A	302 (56.4)		250 (56.2)	52 (57.8)	0.7804
Category B	277 (51.8)		224 (50.3)	53 (58.9)	0.1387
Category C	147 (27.5)		119 (26.7)	28 (31.1)	0.3970
Category D	26 (4.9)		25 (5.6)	1 (1.1)	0.0698
Category E	208 (38.9)		167 (37.5)	41 (45.6)	0.1542
Category F	93 (17.4)		71 (16.0)	22 (24.4)	0.0526
Category G	145 (27.1)		121 (27.2)	24 (26.7)	0.9187
Category H	53 (9.9)		44 (9.9)	9 (10.0)	0.9740

Table 3: Patient-reported outcome measures for the participating patients

	Total (N=535)	Missing N(%)	No (N=445)	Yes (N=90)	p-value
Frail-VIG index on discharge*	0.4 (0.1)		0.4(0.1)	0.4(0.1)	0.1859
Charlson comorbidity index on discharge					
Cerebral vascular disease	132 (24.7)		105(23.6)	27(30)	0.1987
Diabetes	246 (46.0)		200 (44.9)	46 (51.1)	0.2843
COPD	137 (25.6)		117 (26.3)	20 (22.2)	0.4198
Heart failure/ischemic heart disease	351 (65.6)		294 (66.1)	57 (63.3)	0.6185
Dementia	123 (23.0)		100 (22.5)	23 (25.6)	0.5260
Peripheral arterial disease	68 (12.7)		50 (11.2)	18 (20.0)	0.0228
Chronic kidney failure	45 (8.4)		40 (9.0)	5 (5.6)	0.2845
Cancer	98 (18.3)		77 (17.3)	21 (23.3)	0.1774
EQ-5D-5L*	0.5(0.3)	117 (21.9)	0.5(0.3)	0.5(0.3)	0.7217
Adherence to Refill and Medications Scale*	16.6(3.9)	227 (42.4)	16.5(3.9)	16.8(3.7)	0.6802
Barthel Index*	60.1(29.9)	345 (64.5)	60.3(30.3)	59.2(28.2)	0.8562

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Gijon Social and Family Evaluation Scale	7.9(7.6)	48 (9.0)	7.8(7.4)	8.2(8.6)	0.6229
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Table 4: Basic description of the participating caregivers by patient readmission status

	Missing				
	Total (N=535)	N(%)	No (N=445)	Yes (N=90)	p-value
Age*	59(12.5)	183 (34.2)	59.1(12.8)	58.6(11.6)	0.7730
EQ-5D-5L*	0.8(0.3)	25 (4.7)	0.8(0.3)	0.8(0.3)	0.2397
12-item Zarit Burden Interview *	16(10.6)	142 (26.5)	16.3(10.7)	14.5(9.7)	0.1922
